

THE IMPACT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE ON SMOKERS

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Abstract. *The given article describes information regarding smoking, which continues to be the universal leading cause of preventable morbidity and premature death, especially in low- and middle-income countries. It accounts for about 6 million tobacco-related deaths each year, accounting for 10% of all deaths. About half of all lifelong smokers die prematurely, losing an average of 10 years of life. As a direct cause of cardiovascular, cancerous and respiratory diseases, smoking places a huge burden on the health care system. The health risks of tobacco use are well documented. Despite this knowledge and warnings given in the media, the number of smokers is increasing day by day. It is estimated that the number of smokers worldwide is about one billion one hundred million people, two-thirds of whom live in developing countries. The article touches deeply on medical, ethical and social issues related to the influence of physical culture on smokers.*

Keywords: *smoking, sedentary lifestyle, physical activity, physical culture, sports.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that cigarette smoking affects three factors associated with endurance performance: serum hemoglobin levels, lung capacity, and weight loss. Smokers with a higher smoking burden have lower performance capacity, lower heart rate reserve, and blunted heart rate response to exercise.

Objective: To review current evidence on the effects of exercise on smokers.

Materials and methods: A comparative analysis of the scientific literature based on various sources of information.

Results and discussion. Reduced exercise capacity has been described in smokers, even in those, who do not meet current physiological criteria for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and do not lead a particularly sedentary lifestyle. In this context, it is widely recognized that exercise capacity depends on complex cardiopulmonary interactions that support oxygen (O₂) delivery to muscle mitochondria [3]. Although much attention has been given to peripheral muscle factors, O₂ transport abnormalities (including the effects of elevated carboxyhemoglobin) and autonomic nervous system imbalance, more recently other abnormalities have been described, including early microscopic emphysema, pulmonary microvascular disease, ineffective ventilation and gas exchange and left ventricular diastolic dysfunction.

Definitely, blood hemoglobin concentrations are clearly associated with endurance performance and correlate strongly with oxygen-carrying capacity. Decreases in hemoglobin levels are associated with reductions in maximal oxygen consumption and submaximal exercise capacity [1].

Certainly, cigarette smoking has been associated with persistent increases in hemoglobin levels. Smoking 10 or more cigarettes per day is associated with a mean increase in hemoglobin levels of 3.5% compared with nonsmoking controls, a change that can be maintained simply by continuing the treatment regimen. In fact, older adults with longer smoking histories have higher

hemoglobin levels, suggesting a possible dose-dependent effect. During exercise, some smokers may have impaired O₂ delivery to the respiratory muscles, similar to what has been demonstrated in the peripheral muscles of non-COPD smokers at very high ventilation rates. In fact, exercise stress represents a physiologically elegant – and clinically relevant – model for identifying the deleterious effects of oxidative stress, pro-inflammatory status, sustained high circulating nicotine levels, low O₂, and high carbon monoxide on human health long before they become apparent at rest [4].

Although lack of physical activity and perhaps specific psychological characteristics are the main barriers, there appears to be a subgroup of smokers who are particularly intolerant of physical activity. Complex and poorly understood interactions between cardiopulmonary and muscular impairments may underlie this specific phenotype of “exertional symptomatic smokers”. A better understanding of the systemic effects of smoking in subjects who have not (yet) demonstrated evidence of severe smoking-related diseases such as COPD and coronary heart disease may prove useful in combating their ever-growing burden [5]. Recent evidence suggests that aerobic exercise training may attenuate the deleterious effects of cancer risk factors, including smoking. Reactive oxygen species generated during cigarette smoking have been associated with increased expression of inflammatory genes through the induction of NF- κ B and pro-inflammatory mediators, leading to inflammation and epithelial disease progression. Moderate-intensity aerobic exercise training (40-60% VO₂ max) reduces circulating levels of the inflammatory cytokines IL-6 and TNF- α while increasing plasma IL-10 levels. Most of the evidence examining the mechanisms by which exercise may promote smoking cessation comes from experimental studies examining the acute effects of exercise, although it has been argued that most of these mechanisms may also apply to long-term exercise involving regular bouts of physical activity.

Besides that, experimental studies have consistently shown that temporarily abstinent smokers experience reduced psychological withdrawal symptoms and cravings following cardiovascular exercise [1]. Studies with longer periods of exercise have generally demonstrated more sustained effects in reducing craving and withdrawal, and further research is needed to understand how the dose of exercise influences the duration of acute effects. However, even short bouts of exercise with short-term effects may help abstinent smokers cope with temporary cravings. In addition to the potential for exercise to benefit smokers by reducing self-reported withdrawal and cravings, several studies have shown that exercise delays smoking or has beneficial effects on smoking topography, possibly mediated by reductions in craving and withdrawal [3].

Definitely, exercise has some similarities to smoking in its effects on central nervous system stimulation and neurobiological processes, including increased beta-endorphin levels in smokers, and may provide an alternative reinforcer to smoking; there is evidence that this may also depend on the reinforcing value of physical activity compared with smoking for particular individuals [2]. It is plausible that attention to somatic cues (eg, bodily sensations and movements) during exercise may distract smokers from cravings, although one study found that distraction is unlikely to play a significant role. There is also some evidence that exercise may help by reducing attentional bias to smoking-related cues that trigger cravings. There is also evidence that exercise may benefit smokers trying to quit by reducing weight gain after quitting and reducing cravings for sweet foods. Other evidence suggests that regular physical exercise may promote smoking

cessation through exercise-induced increases in smoking-related self-efficacy or through the development of a physically active identity [5].

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that smoking can negatively affect not only cardiopulmonary endurance, in which movements or cycles are repeated, but also speed, namely, instantaneous explosive work. Since smoking can increase proteolysis and inhibit protein synthesis, this can lead to a loss of muscle mass. In addition, smoking impairs the oxygen delivery system to the mitochondria and the production of adenosine triphosphate in the mitochondria; these reduced capabilities can affect muscle contraction and anaerobic training. Physical education has a positive effect on smokers by changing attitudes towards smoking and increasing the level of individual self-efficacy to quit smoking, improving the physical development of the body, physical education normalizes the work of the cardiovascular, respiratory and other systems of the body.

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